

Marketing Strategy based on Analysis of Marketing Mixture on Consumer Purchase Decisions in the Area of Dermo Café Coffee, Malang, Indonesia

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Abstract:

This research was conducted in November 2018 in the Dermo Café Malang area, Indonesian coffee products are one of the superior coffees in the world. Even Indonesia's production is included in the top 3 coffee producing countries besides Brazil and Vietnam. One potential coffee business is the spread of coffee cafes. This happens in Malang city in certain regions. Research aims to: (1) Analyze the influence of marketing mix variables (Product, Promotion, Price, Place, People, Physical Evidence, Process) as a whole on consumer purchasing decisions of coffee products in the cafe area kopi Dermo, Malang; (2) Analyzing marketing mix variables (Product, Promotion, Price, Place, People, Physical Evidence, Process) The sample of this study is 200 respondents who are consumers of coffee cafes at the research location. The research method that will be used is 1) descriptive analysis, 2) SEM analysis. The results obtained that all marketing mix variables include product variables, promotion variables, price variables, place variables, people variables, physical evidence variables, process variables influence the decision to purchase coffee in the Dermo coffee shop in Malang. However, there is one variable that has a negative effect, namely the variable person because for consumers, the appearance of employees, service friendliness is not very influential on consumers in buying coffee products.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The type of research used in this study is quantitative research. Quantitative research method is one type of research whose specifications are systematic, planned, and clearly structured from the beginning to the design of the research. According to Sugiyono (2013), quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods that are based on positivism philosophy, used to examine certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally done randomly, data collection uses research instruments, quantitative or statistical data analysis with the aim of testing the predetermined hypothesis. Quantitative methods are used with consideration of suitability for measuring variables,

namely using a structured questionnaire to answer the research objectives with a Likert scale.

II. METHODS

Determination of samples carried out in this study using purposive sampling method. According to Sugiyono (2013), Purposive Sampling is a sampling method that is done by setting intentionally setting certain criteria or considerations based on the objectives in the study. In this study, the criteria that can be used as samples are as follows:

A) Consumers who come to visit the Dermo coffee cafe area, Malang.

B) Consumers aged 17-60 years who know, know and who consume coffee in the Dermo coffee cafe

area, Malang. Because the number of population is not known with certainty then to save time, effort and cost, the sample size (number of respondents) is determined by Bernoulli as follows:

$$N = [Z \alpha / 2]^2 p.q/e^2$$

In this study used the level of accuracy (α) 5%, 95% confidence level so that the value of $Z = 1.96$ was obtained. The error rate is set at 10%. Meanwhile, the probability of the correct (received) or incorrect (rejected) questionnaire is 0.5. By entering into the equation above, it is obtained:

$$n = [1.96]^2 0.5.0.5 / 0.1^2 = 96.04 \quad 0.01n = 96.04 = 96$$

The resulting calculation is obtained to a minimum of 96, but the researcher took a sample of 200 people.

Method of collecting data

In this study, there are two types of data used including:

Primary data was obtained from interviews with consumers, direct observation during the research and documentation in the Dermo coffee cafe area, Malang.

Secondary data is obtained from data from several documents obtained from agencies or research companies that have been processed. While the literature study was obtained from the literature, reference 2.2 Data Analysis

Before conducting data analysis, first conducting an instrument test includes validity and reliability tests.

a) Test Validity

Validity test is done to prove whether each question in the questionnaire is significant, so that later in processing the questionnaire each of these questions is valid (Saiffudin, 2015). The testing criteria are as follows:

If $r_{count} > r_{tabel}$, then the item is valid

If $r_{count} < r_{tabel}$, then the item is invalid

b) Reliability Test

In this study, using Alpha Cronbach's formula according to Rianse, et al (2008), as follows:

$$r_{11} = [k / (k-1)] [1 - E_{si} / s_t]$$

Where:

r_{11} = Alpha Cronbach's reliability coefficient

k = number of item questions tested

S_i = number of variance skro question items

S_t = skro ter variant (total item k)

According to Riton (2006) in Setiawan, et al (2013), Cronbach's Alpha Criteria are divided into 5 with the same range, namely:

1. Cronbach's Alpha value 0.00-0.20 = less reliable
2. Cronbach's Alpha value 0.21-0.40 = somewhat reliable
3. Cronbach's Alpha value 0.41-0.60 = quite reliable
4. Cronbach's Alpha value 0.61-0.80 = reliable
5. Cronbach's Alpha Value 0.81-1.00 = very reliable

Data analysis methods are used to answer each goal as follows:

1. Descriptive analysis

Descriptive analysis is a method used by collecting data and analyzing data obtained. This can make it easier to provide an explanation of the images and facts that occur in the field.

2. SEM Analysis

Data analysis method uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with WrapPls Software. The capital equation structural steps are as follows:

Designing the Structural Model (inner model)

The design of the structural model of the relationship between latent variables on WPLPLS is based on the formulation of the problem or research hypothesis. In SEM the design of the model is based on theory, but the PLS can be in the form of: Theory, if it already exists

Results of empirical research

Analogy, the relationship between variables in other fields of science Normative, such as government regulations, laws, and so forth Rational. Tighten Measurement Model (outer model) In SEM, the design of the measurement model only refers to the operational definition of the variable, according to the design process of the research instrument. The indicator models in SEM are all reflective, so the design of the measurement model is rarely discussed in detail. On the other hand, in the WrapPLS the design of the measurement model (outer model) becomes very important, which is related to whether the indicator is reflective or formative. Constructing a Path Diagram

If steps one and two have been done, so that the results are easier to understand then it is stated in the form of a path diagram. The path diagram is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. SEM Analysis Diagram

Caption:

- X1 = Product X7 = Process
- X2 = Promotion Y = Purchase Decision
- X3 = Price Y1 = Quantity
- X4 = Place Y2 = Trust or Satisfaction
- X5 = Person Y3 = Loyalty
- X6 = Physical Evidence

Conversion of Path Charts into Equation systems

Outer model, which is a specification of the relationship between latent variables and indicators, also called outer relations or measurement models, defining characteristics of latent variables with indicators. The reflective indicator model can be written as follows:

$$x = \Lambda_x \xi + \varepsilon_x$$

$$y = \Lambda_y \eta + \varepsilon_y$$

Where X and Y are indicators for exogenous latent variables (ξ) and endogenous (η). Suppose that Λ_x and Λ_y are loading matrices which describe as simple regression coefficients that connect latent variables to the indicators. Residuals measured by ε_x and ε_y can be interpreted as measurement errors or noise. The equation formative indicator model can be written as follows:

$$\xi = \Pi_\xi X_i + \delta_x$$

$$\eta = \Pi_\eta Y_i + \delta_y$$

Where ξ , η , X, and Y are the same as the previous equation. Π_x and Π_y are like multiple regression coefficients of latent variables towards indicators, while δ_x and δ_y are residuals of regression. Inner model, which is the specification of the relationship between latent variables (Structural Model), also called inner relations, describes the relationship between latent variables based on the substantive theory of research. equal to one, so location parameters (constant parameters) can be removed from the model. The Equation Model can be written as below: $\eta = \beta\eta + \Gamma\xi + \zeta$

Where η represents an endogenous variable vector (dependent), ξ is a latent exogen vector and ζ is an unexplained variance vector. Because PLS is designed for a recursive model, the relationship between latent variables, applies that each

dependent variable η , or often called a causal chain system of latent variables can be specified as follows:

$$\eta_j = \sum_i \beta_{ji} \eta_i + \sum_i \gamma_{jb} \xi_b + \zeta_j$$

Where γ_{jb} (in the form of a matrix denoted by Γ) is a path coefficient that connects endogenous latent variables (η) with exogenous (ξ). Whereas β_{ji} (in the form of a matrix denoted by β) is the coefficient of the connecting path

endogenous latent variable (η) with endogenous (η); for index I and b ranges. The parameter ζ_j is the inner residual variable.

Parameter Estimation / Estimation

As previously explained, there is an estimation of the outer model and inner model. The outer model analysis algorithm, basically is the process of calculating latent variable data that comes from indicator data. In the WrapPLS program there are 5 outer model algorithms, including;

PLS Regression, which is the inner model does not affect the outer model.

PLS mode M or "MIMIC" or "mixed", namely inner model influencing the outer model.

PLS Mode A, for reflective indicator models.

PLS Mode B, for formative indicator models.

Robust Path Analysis, which is a latent variable data in the form of an average indicator score. Analysis of inner model algorithm is a method and process of calculating path coefficients, namely the coefficient of influence (relationship) between latent variables. On the WirPLS software this algorithm includes:

Linear, the model of the relationship between latent variables is linear.

Wrap2, the relationship between latent variables is a U curve.

Wrap3, the relationship between latent variables in the form of an S curve.

This requires that users be able to determine the hypothetical model, before analysis with WrapPLS is carried out. Model Relations between any variable that is linear, follows the U curve and whichever follows the S curve.

Goodness of Fit

Outer model, is a measurement model or that involves testing the validity and reliability of research instruments. Convergent validity, the correlation between the score of the reflexive indicator and the latent variable skro. For this case loading 0.5 to 0.6 is considered sufficient, the number of indicators per latent variable is not large, ranging from 3 to 7 indicators.

Discriminant validity, reflexive indicator measurement based on cross loading with latent variables. When the cross loading value of each indicator in the relevant variable is the largest compared to cross loading on other latent variables, it is said to be valid. Another method is to compare the square root value of average variance extracted (AVE) of each latent variable with the correlation between variables other latent models, if the square root of average variance extracted (AVE) latent variables is greater than the correlation with all other latent variables, it is said to have good discriminant validity. Recommended measurement values greater than 0.50 and considered valid.

$$AVE = (\sum \lambda_i^2) / (\sum \lambda_i^2 + \sum_i [\text{var}(\epsilon_i)])$$

Table 1. Composite reliability (pc), a group of indicators that measure a variable has good composite reliability if it has a Composite.

Nomer	Model fit and quality indices	Kriteria Fit
1.	Average path coefficient (APC)	$p < 0.05$
2.	Average R-squared (ARS)	$p < 0.05$
3.	Average adjusted R-squared (AARS)	$p < 0.05$
4.	Average block VIF (AVIF)	Acceptable if ≤ 5 , ideally $\leq 3,3$
5.	Average full collinearity VIF (AVFIF)	Acceptable if ≥ 5 , ideally = 3.3
6.	Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)	Small $\geq 0,1$, Medium ≥ 0.25 , Large $\geq 0,36$
7.	Sympson's paradox ratio (SPR)	Acceptable if ≥ 0.7 , ideally = 1
8.	R-squared contribution ratio (RSCR)	Acceptable if ≥ 0.9 , ideally = 1
9.	Statistical suppression ratio (SSR)	Acceptable if ≥ 0.7
10.	Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (NLBCDR)	Acceptable if ≥ 0.7

Objective 2 can be answered using the results of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis using WrapPLS Software. Determination of the most dominant independent variable affects the dependent variable using the regression coefficient value (λ). The purpose of this study is to determine the most dominant variable as a whole, so that the greatest regression coefficient is the most dominant variable that affects the dependent variable.

3.2. Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing is done to test the hypothesis according to the exposure to the goal. The hypothesis tested only answers goal 1. The test is done by the Bootstrap resampling method developed by Geissers and Stone. The test statistics used are t statistics or t tests, with the statistical hypothesis as follows:

The statistical hypothesis for the outer model is:

$$H_0: \lambda_i = 0 \text{ versus } H_1: \lambda_i \neq 0$$

While the statistical hypothesis for inner model: the effect of exogenous latent variables on endogenous is

$$H_0: \gamma_i = 0 \text{ versus } H_1: \gamma_i \neq 0$$

While the statistical hypothesis for inner model: the effect of endogenous latent variables on endogenous is $H_0: \beta_i = 0 \text{ versus } H_1: \beta_i \neq 0$

The application of the resampling method, allows the application of free distributed data, does not require normal distribution assumptions, and does not require large samples, testing is done by t-test, when p-value 5 0.05 (alpha 5%) is obtained, it can

3.3 Performance Indicators

The performance indicators of the research that will be carried out are as follows:

1. Increased number (productivity) and quality of lecturer research indicated by the increasing strength of the laboratory research umbrella, or the updating of teaching materials, or the limited laboratory research methods.

2. The increasing number of students involved in lecturer research, including supporting Pimnas Students.

3. The time for completing the student thesis is reduced.
4. The quality of the thesis increases, seen from the increase in the percentage of the A thesis score.
5. Student satisfaction with the quality of lecturer guidance is increased, indicated by the questionnaire distributed by the Study Program.
6. Students' understanding increases on real problems in the industry, the world of entrepreneurship or agencies related to the field of Agriculture and its ability to solve these problems.
7. The participation of graduates and practitioners in S-1 education.

DISCUSSION

Malang Dermo area is on Highway Dermo, Mulyoagung Village, Dau District, Malang City. This Dermo area is a new area famous for its coffee shops because there are several coffee shops along Jalan Dermo. Various types of coffee shops ranging from cafe scale not only highlight the quality of coffee products but also feature cafe facilities to ordinary coffee shops that are just sell coffee like coffee shops in general. There are six coffee shops that are the location of the study as explained below Gender is a biological factor that distinguishes humans into two groups of men and women. The following are the characteristics of respondents based on sex can be seen in Table 8

No	Gender	Total (Person)	Persentation (%)
1	Male	178	89
2	Female	22	11
Total		200	100

Table 2. Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2018

Based on Table 8 it can be seen that in this study respondents were dominated by male sex as many as 178 people or by 89%. While the remaining 22 people or 11% are female respondents. This shows that drinking coffee is still the majority of men's consumption because of the fact in the field, men

prefer to drink coffee in coffee shops along with their friends.

3.3 Measurement Model

Validity test

Test Validity seen from convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity can be seen from the acquisition of AVE values > 0.50; as presented in Table 13 below.

Table 13. Factor Loading Value

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2018

Processing Results from Table 13. Can be seen in the loading factor showing > 0.50 so that the construct for most indicators is acceptable. Furthermore, the validity of criminalized can be seen from the square root value. Average Variance Extraxted (AVE) and correlation between latent constructs, from yields greater than the value of correlation with all other variables.

5.3.2 Reliability Test

The reliability test of the questionnaire can be seen from the value of composite reliability and the value of cronbach's alpha. The cronbach's alpha value must be > 0.6 and the Composite Reliability value must be > 0.7 as a reliability requirement. In Table 14. Shows that all the questionnaire variables in the study have good reliability so it can be concluded that the questionnaire can be used and developed in research.

Table 3. Test Reliability

Variable	Composite Reliability	Cronbachs Alpha	AVE
Product	0,689	0,408	0,368
Promotion	0,764	0,591	0,485
Price	0,581	0,207	0,416
Place	0,754	0,511	0,507
People	0,708	0,384	0,449
Physical evidence	0,505	0,395	0,250
Process	0,766	0,636	0,421
buying decision	0,741	0,596	0,297

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2018

3.4 Structural Model

The structural model can be seen from the Goodness of Fit (GOF) model which is an index

and measure of the goodness of relations between latent variables. The results of the Goodness of Fit test in Appendix 4, show that the results obtained by the Average Path Coefficient value ($\beta = 0.147$, $p = 0.008$) and Average R-squared by ($\beta = 0.343$, $p < 0.001$). In addition, the AVIF value as an indicator of lateral colinearity obtained was 1.231 and the AFVIF value as an indicator of vertical colinearity was 1,287.

Table 4. Goodness of Fit

Index	Result	Standard Value	Explanation
Average path coefficient (APC)	0.147	P=0.008	Fulfilled
Average R-squared (ARS)	0.343	P<0.001	Fulfilled
Average adjusted R-squared (AARS)	0.319	P<0.001	Fulfilled
Average block VIF (AVIF)	1.231	≤ 3.3	Fulfilled
Average full collinearity VIF (AFVIF)	1.287	≤ 3.3	Fullfilled
GoF	0.370	> 0.1, medium > 0.25, large > 0.36	Large
Sympson's paradox ratio (SPR)	0.857	≥ 0.7	Fulfilled
R-squared contribution ratio (RSCR)	0.984	≥ 0.9	Fulfilled
Statistical suppression ratio (SSR)	1	≥ 0.7	Fulfilled
Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (NLBCDR)	0.929	≥ 0.7	Fulfilled

Source: Primery Data Processed, 2018

Small size of Goodness Tenenhaus (GOF) = 0.10; Medium GOF = 0.25; and large GOF = 0.36; based on the results of the above calculations, the GOF value is 0.370; indicates that the GOF value in the model is included in the big criteria. Testing the inner model or structural model is done to see the relationship between constructs, significance values and R-square of the research model. The R-square value for the product variable is 0.068; for promotion variables obtained 0.013; for the price variable obtained 0.085; place variable obtained 0.069; for the person variable obtained is -0.006; for the physical evidence variable obtained 0.087; for

process variables obtained 0.026. These results indicate that 0.068% of product variables affect purchasing decision variables, 0.013% of promotion variables affect purchasing decision variables, 0.085% of price variables affect purchase decision variables, 0.069% of place variables affect purchasing decision variables, -0.006% of people variables do not affect purchasing decision variables, 0.087% of physical evidence variables

affect purchasing decision variables, 0.026% process variables affect the variable purchasing decisions of consumers of coffee products Dermo coffee shop area, Malang

Gambar 4. SEM Model Evaluation

3.5 Hypothesis Testing

Significant measures of hypothesis support to see the effect of the 7p marketing mix (product, promotion, price, place, person, physical evidence, process) on purchasing decisions of coffee products in the Dermo region, Malang. The results of data analysis in Table 16. This study shows that the seven variables are accepted.

16. Results Hypothesis

Tests in Partial Least Square (PLS) are statistically each hypothesized relationship is carried out by the bootstrap method to minimize the problem of research data abnormalities. In testing this hypothesis, if the path coefficient values are shown

in Table 16 with a significance level of <0.05 , the hypothesis is declared not accepted. Conversely, if the significance level is > 0.05 , the hypothesis is accepted.

1. Hypothesis 1

The results of the first hypothesis state that the product construct has a positive effect on the purchasing decision of coffee products in the Dermo region, Malang because it shows the path coefficient value of 0.19; $P\text{-value} > 0.05$. From table 4 it can be stated that the hypothesis is accepted.

2. Hypothesis 2

The results of the second hypothesis state that the promotion construct has a positive effect on the purchasing decision of coffee products in the Dermo area, Malang because it shows the path coefficient value of 0.09; $P\text{-value} > 0.05$. From table 4 it can be stated that the hypothesis is accepted.

3. Hypothesis 3

The results of the third hypothesis state that the price construct has a positive effect on the purchasing decision of coffee products in the Dermo region, Malang because it shows the path coefficient value of 0.22; $P\text{-value} > 0.05$. From table 4 it can be stated that the hypothesis is accepted.

4. Hypothesis 4

The results of the fourth hypothesis state that the place construct has a positive effect on the purchasing decision of coffee products in the Dermo region, Malang because it shows the path coefficient value of 0.17; $P\text{-value} > 0.05$. From table 4 it can be stated that the hypothesis is accepted.

5. Hypothesis 5

The results of the fifth hypothesis state that people's constructs do not affect the purchasing decisions of coffee products in the Dermo region, Malang, because they show path coefficient values of 0.02; $P\text{-value} > 0.05$. From table 4 it can be stated that the hypothesis is not accepted.

6. Hypothesis 6

The results of the sixth hypothesis state that the physical evidence construct has a positive effect on the purchasing decision of coffee products in the Dermo region, Malang because it shows the path

coefficient value of 0.24; $P\text{-value} > 0.05$. From table 4 it can be stated that the hypothesis is accepted.

7. Hypothesis 7

The results of the seventh hypothesis state that the process construct has a positive effect on the purchasing decision of coffee products in the Dermo region, Malang because it shows the path coefficient value of 0.10; $P\text{-value} > 0.05$. From table 4 it can be stated that the hypothesis is accepted

5.6 Marketing Mix Analysis of Consumer purchasing Decisions

Seven marketing mix variables have an influence on purchasing decisions, including products, promotions, prices, places, people, physical evidence, and processes. It was found that the product, price, place, and physical evidence had a significant influence on consumer purchasing decisions on coffee products in the Dermo Area, Malang. Because consumers consider a variety of beverage and snack products along with affordable prices to make consumers interested in addition to places and supporting facilities consumers are also highly expected to support consumers while buying products in the shop which provides facilities that fulfill and make consumers satisfied in their services.

5.6.1 Relationship of Product Variables to Consumer Purchasing Decisions.

The marketing mix strategy in the product aspect is everything that is prepared to provide products that can meet the wants and needs of consumers. Product aspects include raw materials used in making products, product quality, brands, packaging, labels, and the types of products offered to consumers. According to Tjiptono (2008) products are all things that can be offered by producers to be considered, sought, bought, requested, used, and consumed by the market as fulfilling the needs or desires of the relevant market. In its development, the condition of the coffee shop in the Dermo area, Malang experienced rapid progress. One stalls with other cafe offer a variety of coffee products of various quality. Even the coffee products offered to consumers vary, from Gresik, Dampit, Kintamani, Aceh gayo, and many more. The method of brewing coffee in each stall differs from simple to modern machines. This shows that the product variable is one of the

variables that has a positive influence on consumers or stall owners.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained that all marketing mix variables include product variables, promotion variables, price variables, place variables, people variables, physical evidence variables, process variables influence the decision to purchase coffee in the Dermo coffee shop in Malang. However, there is one variable that has a negative effect, namely the variable person because for consumers, the appearance of employees, service friendliness is not very influential on consumers in buying coffee products.

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